
A REVIEW: NUTRITION IN CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

End-stage renal disease (ESRD) can result from a wide variety of different kidney diseases. Currently, 90% of patients reaching CKD have chronic diabetes mellitus, glomerulonephritis or hypertension. With CKD comes a myriad of problems related to the kidney's inability to excrete waste products leads to symptoms of uraemia. The treatments of CKD require dialysis or kidney transplantation. In this review, an attempt has been made to explain the nutritional management of CKD along with various dialysis treatment and the complications related to the dialysis method. It is important to maintain optimal nutritional status so that the patient will be a good candidate to respond to the treatment effectively. Kidney Patients necessitate following a balanced diet plan to retain normal protein stores and to avoid metabolic complications. This article deals with the therapeutic aspects of nutrition in CKD patients and will improve the quality of life

Keywords: ESRD, CKD, Dialysis, Nutritional management.

INTRODUCTION

The kidney is the human organ basically responsible for the filtration of nitrogenous and other metabolic waste products from the body through the urinary system and maintains the metabolism of biochemical especially haemostatics fluid, electrolyte and acid-base balance. (1) Another key biochemical function of the kidney is to help maintain blood pressure, activate vitamin D and produce erythropoietin. But, the efficiency of the kidney is a decline when there is a loss of nephron function.(2)

A chronic renal failure which is also known uremia is a drastically high level of urea in the blood which may be the end result of acute glomerulonephritis and nephrotic syndrome.(3, 4) CRF is a slowly progressive loss of renal function over a period of month or year resulting in abnormally low glomerular filtration rate which is usually determined indirectly by the creatinine level in the blood serum.(5)

The persons with stage 4 chronic kidney disease (CKD) have advanced kidney damage with a severe decrease in the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) to 15-30 ml/min (6,7). In the management of ESRD, dialysis is used on either temporary basis or permanent basis. There may be a possibility of a kidney transplant in the near future. Dialysis is an artificial process by which nitrogenous waste products are removed from the blood in the event of kidney failure (8,9). There is two main type of dialysis – hemodialysis and peritoneal dialysis. In hemodialysis, the blood is purified outside the body via an automated machine, and in the process of peritoneal dialysis, the blood is filtered through the peritoneal membrane located in the abdomen. The common characteristic adoption of both types of dialysis is the removal of the wastes and excess fluids from the body (10).

CAUSES OF CKD

There can be several causes of CKD which includes immune complex Glomerulonephritis, chronic pyelonephritis, metabolic diseases with renal involvement as Diabetes mellitus, especially IDDM, HT, toxic substances or drugs like Paracetamol, Crocin, Diclofenac sodium, Vovron, Aspirin, Carbon tetrachloride, anti-inflammatory drugs, certain poisonous mushrooms(11,12,13). CKD may also occur from immunological reaction to drugs like certain Antibiotics. The conditions of CKD can also be due to infections causing obstructions of the urinary tract like stones calcium phosphate, calcium oxalate and uric acid. The other probable causes are hypertension, renal tubular disease, renal vascular diseases, congenital abnormalities like a polycystic disease, gout and abdominal surgical emergency, chronic malnutrition (14,15). Generally, the urine output depends upon GFR. Once renal failure occur the normal functions of kidney like regulation of body fluids, electrolytes, PH and excretion of metabolites are disrupted. (16)

COMPLICATIONS OF CKD

The major complication of CKD is Osteodystrophy leading to anaemia. This particularly occurs due to failure in controlling Ca and P levels due to a disturbance in two metabolic functions i.e. activation of Vit. D and action of parathyroid hormones (17,18). The symptoms of Osteodystrophy is generally manifested in the form of bone pain, various bone deformities, gait, tiredness, breathlessness on exertion, bleeding due to abnormal platelet function. CKD also affect nervous system which leads to muscle twitching, burning

sensation in extremities and convulsions. This can be prevented by reducing phosphate in diets like restriction PO₄ rich foods like milk, whole grain, bread etc (19).

COMPLICATION IN HAEMODIALYSIS

Hypotension: It is a most acute complication of the Hemodialysis. Many dialytic and patient-related factors influence blood pressure during the treatment cardiac output and blood pressure must be maintained by an increase heart rate and in some instances by an increase in myocardial contractility(20). However, the large burden of cardiovascular disease in Hemodialysis population often limits the ability of the heart to respond appropriately to the stress of fluid removal. These inherently different responses to ultrafiltration and diffusion greatly influence the maintenance of blood pressure during Hemodialysis (21)

Cramps: Muscle cramps occur in as many as 20% of dialysis treatment. Cramps are known to be more frequent when ultra filtration rates very high. And when dialysate with low sodium concentration is employed, an indication that cramps are caused by acute extra cellular volume contraction (22)

Arrhythmias and Angina: Patient with ESRD frequently have several predisposing factors for arrhythmias. There is a high prevalence of left ventricular hypertrophy and valvular sclerosis. Coronary artery disease is common in the dialysis population, and pericardial effusions are frequently revealed by echocardiography (23,24). The reasons behind this are the rapid changes in electrolyte concentrations inherent in efficient Hemodialysis. It is not surprising that Hemodialysis may provoke cardiac arrhythmias. Angina frequently occurs during dialysis. The anaemia associated with chronic renal failure adds to the risk of episodes of angina(25).

Hypoxia: Hypoxia occurs during Hemodialysis is influenced by the nature of the buffer used in the dialysate and by the type of membrane in the artificial kidney. The arterial Pco₂ in acetate buffered dialysate is low, creating a diffusion gradient from blood to the dialysate. Because carbon dioxide is removed from the blood into the dialysate, there is decreased in the respiratory drive. The second factor influencing the magnitude of hypoxia that occurs during dialysis is the type of membrane used. Hypoxia is noted when patients are dialyzed against a bioincompatible membrane such as a cellulosic membrane. (26, 27)

Hypoglycemia: Carbohydrate metabolism is quite abnormal in patients with chronic renal failure. A diabetic patient who takes a usual dose of insulin may experience hypoglycemia when undergoing dialysis against a bath with a fixed glucose concentration (that is glucose clamp) and too low for the amount of insulin being administered (28, 29). It is frequently necessary to decrease the dose of insulin on dialysis days to prevent hypoglycemic episodes. (30)

Haemorrhage: The uremic environment produces impaired platelet functioning, changes in capillary permeability and anaemia, all of which can impair homeostasis. Patient undergoing Hemodialysis still has a higher risk of the hemorrhagic event because of repeated exposure to heparin (31). Heparin is used to prevent clotting in the extracorporeal circuit. In addition to acute bleeding episodes, a patient undergoing Hemodialysis is exposed to chronic, low-grade episodes of blood loss with each dialysis treatment.(32,33,)

COMPLICATION IN PERITONEAL DIALYSIS

Cardiovascular disease: It is a major cause of death in PD patients. The rate of CVD is higher in dialysis patients than in the general population. The multifactorial atherosclerotic risk factor in PD patient includes not only the traditional risk factors of smoking, hypertension, family history, obesity but also coronary calcification, hypoalbuminemia, hyper-homocystinemia.(34,35)

Hypertension: Hypertension is very common. It occurs in 50 to 90% of PD patients. It may be explained in part by fluid retention as a result of impaired ultrafiltration(36,37). **Hyperlipidemia:** PD is associated with an increased glucose load because of constant absorption from the peritoneal cavity. Because of this glucose load, PD patient has a constant susceptibility to the development of hyperglycemia and hyperinsulinemia. This increases insulin levels result in an increase in the synthesis of triglycerides in the liver, In addition, dialysate protein loss of 5 to 15 gm per day results in the loss of all lipoproteins, with preferential loss of small molecules such as HDL.(38,39)

DIALYSIS IN ESRD

Dialysis is the procedure that replaces some of the kidney's normal function. It is performed when a person experience kidney failure, usually when more than 95% of kidney function is lost in both kidneys. Dialysis keeps the body balanced by removing waste products including salt and excess fluid, maintaining a safe level of blood chemicals such as Na, K & Cl and controlling blood pressure (40). It is of two types:-

Hemodialysis

Peritoneal dialysis

Hemodialysis: It is widely performed. Assess to the vascular system is by means of Scribner shunts, atriovenous fistulas, and grafts. The actual dialyzer may be of parallel plate, coil, or hollow fibre type. Body solutes & excessive body fluid can be easily cleared by using dialysate fluids of the known chemical composition. In this process blood passes by the semipermeable membrane of the artificial kidney and waste products are removed by diffusion and restore the body's chemical balance. Non dialyzed uremic patients can digest 0.5 to 0.6 gm per kg. body wt. protein. Clinically stable patients can ingest 1.13 gm. per day protein and 23 to 24 kcal per kg body wt. per day.(42)

DIETARY MANAGEMENT OF CKD

Energy: Energy requirement of the renal patients is based on their sex, height, weight, and type of work (sedentary or moderate). Sufficient non-protein calories in the form of carbohydrates and fats is essential to spare protein for protein synthesis and energy needs 32- 38 kcal/kg/day for adults and 100-150 kcal/kg/day in case of children. Generally, 300-400gm Carbohydrate should be provided daily preferably in the form of simple carbohydrates like sugar, honey, glucose etc.(41,)

Protein: 0.5-0.8gms/kg body weight of protein per day is required with 60-70% as high biological value protein. This requirement is to reduce azotemia hyperkalemia and acidosis. Sources should include Essential Amino Acids from milk egg etc. Protein requirement ranges from 20-60 gm/day of high biological value, 50% from animal sources and 50% from plant sources. (42)

Carbohydrates: Sufficient amount of carbohydrate to meet the energy requirement to prevent starvation ketosis, reduce catabolism of protein, to have protein sparing action. (43). Generally, 300-400 gms/ day in form of refined and complex carbohydrate are preferred.(44)

Fats: Unsaturated fats are preferred to saturated fat. The ratio of PUFA: SFA should be 1:1. Emulsified fat like cream, butter are preferred(45).

Sodium: Ideal intake-1-2mmol/kg (infant) 40-60 mmol/day older child or 500mg -2.0 gms/day in adults (46, 47). Strict restriction is required if hypertension and oedema. 2 mmol/kg body weight/day & diuretic until crises are over. Diminished kidney function leads to sodium imbalance; any sudden increase in sodium intake cannot be excreted and may cause more edema (48, 49, 50)

Potassium: Potassium level in CRF can be either elevated or depressed. Vomiting and diarrhea leads to hypokalemia in which small dose of potassium may be needed (51). Severe Glomerular filtration failure results in hyperkalemia which leads to increase in serum potassium level resulting in cardiac arrest (52, 53, 54). So potassium rich food like tomato, juices, coffee, tea, cocoa, potassium rich vegetables should be avoided. Potassium intake should be 1500mg/day (35-40mEq/day (55, 56).

Phosphorus, Sulphate, Organic Acid: There deficiency leads to reduced nephron function and reduced filtration and excretion of these material leads to acidosis (57, 58)

Calcium and phosphorus: When GFR falls 20-30% below normal hyperphosphatemia occurs. Hyperthyroidism leads to hypocalcemia resulting in osteodystrophy. Phosphorus intake is restricted 800-1200mg/day(59, 60). Phosphate binding agents may be used if required to reduce absorption. Calcium supplements are also recommended. Calcium intake of 1 to 2 gms/ day is advised (61, 62). Do not start calcium supplements, unless phosphate is restricted, to avoid soft tissue calcification. Calcium carbonate supplements can help buffer metabolic acidosis. Multivitamin supplements are required. Supplement of vitamin D3 may be recommended based on needs (63, 64).

Water: Fluid is limited to urinary output +/-500 ml per day. Total intake must account for additional fluids in the foods consumed and in water derived from metabolism of food nutrients and fecal fluids losses (65, 66, 67).

Vitamins: Limitations in protein and mineral consumption of vitamin deficiency diet. Multivitamin supplement should be providing to correct osteodystrophy vitamin D should be supplemented other vitamins like folic acid and B₆ should also be provided. Vitamin E prevents oxidate stress in dialysis patients.(68, 69, 70, 71, 72)

DIETARY MANAGEMENT OF HEMODIALYSIS

Energy: 35 kcal per kg ideal body weight (table-2). Excessive body weight and protein energy malnutrition should be avoided (73). The prescribed amount of calories has protein sparing action and also it reduces protein catabolism and starvation keto acidosis (74).

Protein: Protein requirement increases due to the dialysate losses and catabolism in hemodialysis patients NKF-DOQI suggests the mean protein requirements for 1.2 g/kg/day in HD patients, respectively (42). According to ESPEN, adjusted diet protein should be consumed as 1.1-1.2 g / kg / day and should be high in the biological value (of animal origin) of 50 % protein in hemodialysis patients (Table 1)

Sodium: When patients drink too much fluid it may actually dilute their Na may be high. Too much Na and water raise blood pressure and results in water retention, pulmonary edema (75). When sodium intake is high check fluid status, if high fluid gains, tell patient to eat fewer salty foods. Eat less salt in diet and fluid. Check fluid status to check whether patient is probably drinking too much Fluid. Limit wt. gains to under 4% of body wt. and ask them to eat fewer salty foods & to limit fluid to 3 cups + urine output. If low fluid gains, make sure they are gaining about 1.5 kg body wt. and are not dehydrated. 2 to 3 gm per day sodium should be given. Sodium benzoate, potassium meta bisulphate added as preservative in pickles, squashes and canned food should be avoided. Commercial soft drinks, proprietary drinks, dry foods like fish, fruits and soup cubes should be avoided(76,77).

Potassium: 2 to 3 gm per day of potassium is recommended (78, 79). When the kidneys do not work properly, potassium builds up in the body and cause the heartbeat unevenly and stop suddenly (80, 81). Too little potassium can also be dangerous. Leaching of vegetables is done to reduce potassium content (82, 83).

Phosphorus: 1to 1.2 gm per day of phosphorus is recommended (84,). It is a minerals found in all the foods but especially present in milk products (85, 86). There must be a balanced between the calcium and phosphorous in the body (87, 88). To maintain calcium phosphorous balance, protein and phosphorous intake needs restriction (89,90).

Fluid intake: In dialysis there is danger of both water intoxication from overloading and dehydration due to little water intake or vomiting or diarrhea (91,92). Fluid intake should monitor carefully. 24 hrs urine output + 500 to 700 ml fluid is sufficient in condition of Oliguria (93, 94).

Table-1: Protein Requirement and Dietary Allowance for Indian Infants, Boys, Girls and Adults on Hemodialysis

	Requirent g/protein/kg/d	Body weight (Kg)	for HD Patient Total daily Requirement g protein/d + 0.4 g/kg/d & +0.2 for adults	Requirement g protein/d	Body weight (Kg)	for HD Patient Total daily Requirement g protein/d + 0.4 g/kg/d and +0.2.g/kg for adults
Infant 1-5 months	2.2	5.0	11.0			
Infant 6-9 months	1.69	7.9	16.5			
Infant 9-12 months	1.69	8.8	18.39			
Boys			Girls			
1-2 years	1.47	10.3	19.26	1.47	9.6	17.9
2-3 years	1.25	12.8	21.1	1.25	12.1	19.9
3-4 years	1.16	14.8	23.0	1.16	14.5	22.6
4-5 years	1.11	16.5	24.9	1.11	16.0	24.1
5-6 years	1.09	18.7	27.8	1.09	17.7	26.3
6-7 years	1.15	20.4	31.62	1.15	20.0	31.0
7-8 years	1.17	22.7	35.6	1.17	22.3	35.0
8-9 years	1.18	25.2	39.8	1.18	25.0	39.5
9-10 years	1.18	28.0	44.2	1.18	27.6	43.6
10-11 years	1.18	30.8	48.6	1.18	31.2	49.2
11-12 years	1.16	34.1	53.1	1.15	34.8	53.9
12-13 years	1.15	38.0	58.9	1.14	39.0	54.6
13-14 years	1.15	43.3	67.1	1.13	43.4	66.4
14-15 years	1.14	48.0	73.9	1.12	47.1	71.5
15-16 years	1.13	51.5	78.7	1.09	49.4	73.6

16-17 years	1.12	54.3	82.5	1.07	51.3	75.4
17-18 years	1.10	56.5	84.75	1.06	52.8	75.9
Adult male	1.0	60	72			
Adult female	1.0	55	66			

Guidelines for Dialysis Centre. Directorate General of Health Services. Government of India

*Values are based on ICMR published Indian standards. In terms of mixed Indian vegetarian diet protein PDCAAS varies from 77.4 to 79.0% for different age groups.

*In children protein loss is inversely proportional to age. Hence protein requirement/d +0.4/kg/d = 0.4 is the increment to achieve positive nitrogen balance.

RECOMMENDED DIETARY NUTRIENT INTAKE FOR HEMODIALYSIS PATIENTS ARE SHOWN BELOW IN TABLE -2 (42, 73, 95, 96, 97).

Nutrients	Recommended intake
Dietary protein intake (DPI)	• 1.2 g/kg/d for clinically stable patients (at least 50% should be of high biological value)
Daily energy intake (DEI)	• 35 kcal/kg/d if <60 years • 30–35 kcal/kg/d if 60 years or older
Total fat	25–35% of total energy intake
Saturated fat	<7% of total energy intake
Polyunsaturated fatty acids	Up to 10% of total calories
Monounsaturated fatty acids	Up to 20% of total calories
Carbohydrate	Rest of calories (complex carbohydrates preferred)
Total fiber	>20–25 g/d
Minerals and Water (Range of Intake)	
Sodium	750–2000 mg/d
Potassium	2000-2750 mg/d
Phosphorus	800-1000 mg/d
Calcium	<1000 mg/d
Magnesium	200–300 mg/d
Iron	10-18 mg/d
Zinc	15 mg/d
Selenium	55 µg/d

Nutrients	Recommended intake
Water	Usually 750–1500 mL/d
Vitamins (Including Dietary Supplements)	
Vitamin B1 (thiamin)	1.1–1.2 mg/d
Vitamin B2 (riboflavin)	1.1–1.3 mg/d
Pantothenic acid	5 mg/d
Biotin	30 µg/d
Niacin	14–16 mg/d
Vitamin B6 (pyridoxine)	10 mg/d
Vitamin B12	2.4 µg/d
Vitamin C	75–90 mg/d
Folic Acid	1–5 mg/d
Vitamin A	800-1000 µg/d
Vitamin D	1000-1500 IU
Vitamin E	400–800 IU

PERITONEAL DIALYSIS

Peritoneal dialysis is used electively or when circumstances prohibit chronic hemodialysis (98). In this dialysis improved soft catheters can be used repeatedly in comparison to Hemodialysis. In this type the patient's blood is cleaned within the body. The blood stays in the blood vessels which line the patient's abdominal space (99).

DIETARY MANAGEMENT IN PERITONEAL DIALYSIS

Table-3: Recommendations for protein and energy supply in adult patients on routine Hemodialysis and CAPD (100).

	ESPEN	NKF
Protein intake (g/kg BW/day)	1.2–1.4 (450% HBV)	1.2 (450%HBV) Hemodialysis
CAPD	1.2–1.5 (450% HBV)	1.2–1.3 (450% HBV)
Energy intake (kcal/kg BW/day)		
Haemodialysis and CAPD*	35	<60 yr 35 <60 yr 30

ESPEN, European Society for Clinical Nutrition and Metabolism; NKF, National Kidney Foundation; CAPD, chronic ambulatory peritoneal dialysis. Including energy supply (glucose) from dialysis. HBV = high biological value.

Table-3: Mineral requirements of patients on HD, haemodialysis; CAPD, chronic ambulatory peritoneal dialysis (101)

Phosphate (mg/d)	800–1000
Potassium (mg/g)	2000–2500
Sodium (g/d)	1.8–2.5
Fluid (ml)	1000+urine volume

*Individual CKD patient's requirements may differ in acute conditions

Energy intake of 25 kcal per kg body weight per day, the protein intake of 1.2 to 1.3 gm per kg per day (11). ($\geq 50\%$ of high biological value), 30 gm of fat per day, PUFA: SFA- 1:1(101), cholesterol intake ≤ 300 mg per day, sodium intake of 750 to 1000 mg per day, potassium intake of 40 to 70 mEq per day, phosphorus intake of 8 to 17 mg per kg per day, calcium intake of 1400 to 1600 mg per day, iron intake sufficient to maintain serum iron level and zinc intake of 15mg per day is recommended(102,103).

CONCLUSION

The hemodialysis therapy should be dealt with by a multidisciplinary team, as recommended for other high risk populations. A part of medical nutrition therapy is to provide nutrition education and periodic counseling by dietitians. For effective intervention, dietitians should present a guide for educating HD patients about individual nutritional needs. This guide should provide information about food sources, nutrients and usage exchange food lists. Adapting to patients requirements of intakes should be based on their laboratory values. Patients may be predisposed to receiving lower than recommended amounts of energy and macro-nutrients to the diet and patients who received information or counseling about their diet must be followed up closely by renal dietitians.

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